

Substitution effect on metal complexes of 2-hydroxybenzoic acid

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Stability constants of 2-hydroxybenzoic acid, 2-hydroxy, 5-sulphobenzoic acid and 2-hydroxy, 3-methyl, 5-sulphobenzoic acid with metal ions Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} have been determined by pH titration technique at an ionic strength of 0.1 NaClO₄. The trend in the stability constant reveals that the electronic effects of the substituents play an important role and it is possible to predict the value of stability constant of substituted 2-hydroxybenzoic acid from the value of parent acid to certain extent.

The electronic effects of the substituents on stability constants of metal complexes have been interpreted according to the current organic chemical theory. The groups capable of contributing electrons to the ring increase the complex stability, whereas the groups attracting electrons decrease the complex stability. In order to see the electronic effects of the substituents on the stability constants of metal complexes we have taken 2-hydroxybenzoic acid and two of its derivatives, because 2-hydroxybenzoic acid forms metal complexes with a number of divalent metal ions of first transition series. The interest towards the study of metal complexes of 2-hydroxybenzoic acid and its various derivatives continued for a long time¹. In this paper we have taken two derivatives of 2-hydroxybenzoic acid (SA), 2-hydroxy, 5-sulphobenzoic acid (SSA) which has an electron withdrawing group and 2-hydroxy, 3-methyl, 5-sulphobenzoic acid (SOCA) which has an electron donating group as well as electron withdrawing group and have studied the complexes of these ligands with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} ions by pH-titration technique. Utility of the study is to find out the substitution effect could be helpful in predicting the value of stability constant of metal complexes.

Results and discussion

It is clear from Table 1 that the substitution of sulphonic acid group has marked influence on the dissociation of phenolic group and has little effect on the dissociation of carboxyl group. Hence the groups capable of contributing electrons to the ring increases the basicity of the phenolic group and therefore it is expected that the complex stability will be higher in this case, whereas the group which attract elec-

tron decreases the phenolic basicity and complex stability as well.

Table 1. Value of dissociation constants

Ligand	pK (carboxyl)	pK (phenolic)
2-Hydroxybenzoic acid	2.81	13.61
2-Hydroxy, 5-sulphobenzoic acid	2.44	11.99
2-Hydroxy, 3-methyl, 5-sulphobenzoic acid	2.55	12.67

The substitution of electron withdrawing sulphonic acid group does decrease the pK value of phenolic group (Table 1) whereas methyl group increases the pK value. We also observe that stability constant of metal complex of 2-hydroxy, 5-sulphobenzoic acid is somewhat lower than the value of corresponding complex of 2-hydroxybenzoic acid which is expected because of presence of sulphonic acid (Table 2). However, when a methyl group is substituted in

Table 2. Stability constants of salicylates of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}

I = 0.1 (NaClO₄), Temp. = 25 ± 1°

Metal ions	SA		SSA		SoCA	
	log <i>k</i> ₁	log <i>k</i> ₂	log <i>k</i> ₁	log <i>k</i> ₂	log <i>k</i> ₁	log <i>k</i> ₂
Mn ²⁺	5.90	3.9	5.25 (5.25)	–	(5.43)	–
Co ²⁺	6.75	4.7	6.05 (6.04)	–	(5.99)	–
Ni ²⁺	6.95	4.8	6.30 (6.30)	–	(6.14)	–
Zn ²⁺	6.85	–	(6.24)	–	–	–

The values given in brackets are obtained from linear plots, whereas other values given are evaluated from formation curve.

2-hydroxy, 5-sulphobenzoic acid in 3-position, the stability constant value increases but values are definitely lower than stability constant of corresponding complex of 2-hydroxybenzoic acid. This is also in consonance with the σ value of these substituents. Thus it is possible to predict the trend in stability constant of complexes formed by various metal ions with different derivatives of 2-hydroxybenzoic acid from the value of stability constants of corresponding complexes 2-hydroxybenzoic acid.

Experimental

The preparation of 2-hydroxy, 3-methyl, 5-sulphobenzoic acid has been described in earlier paper². 2-Hydroxy benzoic acid and 2-hydroxy, 5-sulphobenzoic acid (E. Merck) was commercially available. The stock solution of each ligand was prepared by dissolving a known amount of the substance in water followed by standardization of the solution by usual procedure. The solutions of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} ions were prepared by dissolving a known amount of their sulphates in water. For determination of stability constants Calvin and Wilson's³ extension of Bjerrum's method as adopted by Singh and Banks⁴ was used.

The quantity \bar{n} , the average number of ligands bound per metal ion, was calculated from the difference of the two titration curves. The free ligand concentration was then calculated from the relationship

$$[L] = \frac{L^{\circ} - \bar{n}M^{\circ}}{\phi}$$

where $\phi = 1 + [H] / Kc_3 + [H]^2 / Kc_2 Kc_3$. Kc_2 and Kc_3 are the carboxyl and phenolic dissociation constants (concentration quotients) respectively. The value of Kc_2 and Kc_3 were calculated from the apparent dissociation constants

(Table 1) reported earlier⁵. Knowing \bar{n} and $[L]$, the stability constant values were calculated from usual methods⁶. In another set of experiment the ligand to metal ratio was kept 10, but it did not alter the log k values. All experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 1^{\circ}$ and ionic strength of 0.1 ($NaClO_4$).

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